

SINGLE WOMAN PARENTS' TYPOLOGY OF STRAIN PERSPECTIVES: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL INQUIRY

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Abstract

Work and family life balance is a challenge for single parents worldwide. This explanatory sequential inquiry aimed to identify the motherhood–workplace negotiation ideologies labelled as reinvented motherhood, work–family symbiosis, work-centered motherhood, and work–family conflicted motherhood; challenges, key drivers; support systems; and management strategies used to achieve work-life balance of 60 single woman parents. Mean, frequency and percentage, SD, Mann-Whitney were used in the quantitative analyses and FGD composed of 12 participants was conducted to answer the qualitative research objectives. Results showed a lean motherhood ideology and flexible workplace behavior among single mothers and there were no significant differences in their perspectives when grouped as to age, education, and number of children. The qualitative analyses resulted in emerging themes on challenges of single woman parents described as emotionally and financially challenged, time deficient, and gossiping tendencies. Key drivers were physical and emotional attachment, self-motivation, family support, friends, devotion, work, and personal ideology. Lastly, management strategies include manage your time, ask assistance from others, budget daily income, seek parental support, earn additional income, be flexible, and raise independent children. The results point out at the government to have programs in improving the work–life balance of single woman parents.

Keywords: Single Woman Parents, Strain Perspectives, Explanatory Sequential Inquiry, Iloilo, Philippines.

INTRODUCTION

Rationale of the Study

Mothers are directly affected by the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by the UN in 2015, which has become the overarching framework for United Nations work. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 20230 Agenda are a great hope for mothers around the world especially the poorest, living in rural areas or in remote areas that will mark their life and their children. The recognition and empowerment of mothers can have major positive effects on many of these SDGs. By supporting mothers and their children, the return on investment is largely positive for the realization of the 2030 agenda. Therefore, mothers must be recognized as agents of change who, when educated and adequately supported, can greatly contribute to many of these goals (Make Mothers Matter, 2024).

In support, the Magna Carta of Women (RA 9710) mandates the government to provide the necessary mechanisms to enforce women's rights and adopt and undertake all legal measures necessary to foster and promote the equal opportunity for women to participate in and contribute to the development of the political, economic, social, and cultural realms. To ensure the full integration of women's concerns in the mainstream of development, the government shall provide ample opportunities to enhance and develop their skills,

acquire productive employment and contribute to their families and communities to the fullest of their capabilities. To attain this, women in all sectors must be allowed to participate in policy formulation, planning, organization, implementation, management, monitoring, and evaluation of all programs, projects, and services. It shall support policies, researches, technology, and training programs and other support services such as financing, production, and marketing to encourage active participation of women in national development (<https://cws.up.edu.ph>).

Nowadays, the combination of work and family life is a challenge for many people in society especially single parents who have the worst work–life balance (Van den Eynde et al. 2019). This is partially due to the need for an increase in time spent at work after separation (Thielemans and Mortelmans, 2019). Moreover, this need is especially apparent for women. Single women parents attempt to reduce their financial dependence and is tied to the financial strain perspective. Second, labor market participation causes stress in the roles played by parents in the family system and their labor force participation is tied to the gendered institution perspective (Killewald 2016). The stress related to the introduction of new roles in the household can cause conflict when women want to renegotiate task specialization after entering the labor market. Third, there is an increase in work time and the lack of a partner with whom to share household tasks has been found to generate a general increase in work–life conflict (Bakker and Karsten as cited by Make Mothers Matter, 2024). Nonetheless, work–life conflict is not only a problem with respect to work.

In the Philippines, the government and its people struggle to remove the established perception that society responds to single parents' predicament. These viewpoints diminished the value of single parents and altered their household's feeling of purpose and duty (Garcia et al. as cited by Natividad & San Mateo, 2024). The difficulties they face are less visible and appear to be minimized. In the context of work-life balance, single parents frequently confront exclusive barriers that affect their life satisfaction.

In support to the natural and primary rights and duty of solo parents in rearing their children, Republic Act No. 11861 was enacted to extend assistance in social service and welfare benefits, with the end view of uplifting the status and circumstances of solo parents. It is an act granting benefits to solo parents, amending for the purpose Republic Act No. 8972, entitled “An act providing for benefits and privileges to solo parents and their children, appropriating funds therefor and for other purposes.

However, thousands of single mothers still cope with countless obstacles on a daily basis. Single mothers deserve more understanding, forbearance, embrace, and economic aid in and from society. They work twice as hard as a two parent family not only provide home and food for their children, but also ensure that the home is a secure place in which they can grow up healthy and happy (Martinez, Lee, Francisco, Ahmed, & Jung, 2022).

Further, the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) initiated the Solo Parent Cash Aid in parallel with Republic Act 8972, commonly known as the Solo Parents Welfare Act of 2000. It is a financial assistance program dedicated to offering support to solo parents and tailored to their specific needs. The financial aid is designed to assist

with essential expenses related to child-rearing, such as education, healthcare, and daily living costs. Its aim is to empower solo parents by providing them with the necessary resources to ensure the well-being and development of their children (DSWD, 2024).

As reported by De Castro (2023), the total population of single parents in the Philippines has been projected to be 14 million to 15 million, according to World Health Organization-funded research conducted by the Department of Health (DOH) and the University of the Philippines-National Institutes of Health. The most recent data from the government and non-governmental organizations, nine out of 10 single parents in the Philippines are women, frequently needing more help. Teenage moms, in particular, continue to be particularly at risk. They were more likely to skip school to look after their children, forcing them to seek employment instead, mainly if their partners had abandoned them (Fajardo-Jarilla, 2023). Therefore, this study was carried out to address these gaps.

Objectives of the Study

Generally, this study was conducted to determine the perspectives on motherhood and the workplace of women solo parents in the Municipality of Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo for Fiscal Year 2024. It also assessed other domains such as internal and external drivers to face the challenges of balancing work and family, support systems and management strategies. Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. Determine the motherhood–workplace negotiation perspectives of solo parents in terms of (a) Reinvented motherhood, (b) Work–family symbiosis, (c) Work-centered motherhood, and (d) Work–family conflicted motherhood when taken as an entire group and categorized as to socio-economic elements such as age, education, employment, and number of children;
2. Determine if significant variations exist in the motherhood–workplace negotiation perspectives of solo parents in terms of (a) Reinvented motherhood, (b) work–family symbiosis, (c) work-centered motherhood, and (d) work–family conflicted motherhood when categorized as to socio-economic elements such as age, education, employment, and number of children;
3. Determine the challenges do single woman parents face as they do their job;
4. Determine the internal and external drivers of women solo parents that allow them to face the challenges of balancing work and family;
5. Determine the support systems do women solo parents utilize to achieve work-life balance;
6. Determine the management strategies (other life domains) do women solo parents utilize to achieve work-life balance; and

METHODOLOGY

The researcher utilized the mixed-methods research using the Explanatory Sequential Approach. Wherein, the quantitative data will be collected and analyzed first, followed by the qualitative data that will explain and contextualize the quantitative findings.

(<https://www.scribbr.com>). This study was conducted in the Municipality of Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo from August to October 2024. This study utilized the 60 out of 105 single parents who are members of the Solo Parent Association in the Municipality of Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo Philippines for Fiscal Year 2024. Only 60 single woman parents answered the survey questionnaire. Of the number, twelve (12) are officers of the Association who voluntarily participated in the Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The selection criteria for FGD are: (1) Someone with the most number of children, (2) Someone who has longer number of years in the association, and (3) Someone who holds a position in the association. It utilized the purposive sampling technique (also known as purposeful sampling) in the actual selection of the participants for the said study. Purposeful sampling is a technique widely used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases for the most effective use of limited resources. This involves identifying and selecting individuals or groups of individuals that are especially knowledgeable about or experienced with a phenomenon of interest. In addition to knowledge and experience, the importance of availability and willingness to participate, and the ability to communicate experiences and opinions in an articulate, expressive, and reflective manner (Patton; Cresswell & Plano Clark; Bernard; Spradley as cited by Palinkas, Horwitz, Green, Wisdom, Duan, & Hoagwood, 2015).

The data were generated through the use of a researcher-made questionnaire checklist subjected to validity and reliability testing. Part (1) was used to determine the participants' demographic profile such as age, highest educational attainment and number of children. Part (II), is the questionnaire checklist on the typology of strain perspectives composed of four motherhood–workplace negotiation perspectives namely: (a) Reinvented motherhood (15 items), (b) work–family symbiosis (15 items), (c) work-centered motherhood (15 items), and (d) work–family conflicted motherhood (15 items).

The items on the questionnaires were constructed based on the qualitative data of Gasse and Montelmans (2020) on the perspectives taken by single mothers when combining work and motherhood in a stressful work–life pattern. After quantitative data were collected, coded, and tabulated quantitative analyses were undertaken using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 at .05 significant level. Descriptive statistics such as Mean, frequency and percentage, Standard Deviation, Mann-Whitney were used in the analyses. Responses of the participants in the interview were transcribed, analyzed, and interpreted.

Response Mode on the Typology of Strain Perspective

Index	Semantic Differential	Scale	Verbal Description	Definition
5	Strongly Agree	4.01-5.00	To a Great Extent	Every time
4	Agree	3.01-4.00	Much	Usually 90% of the time
3	Moderately Agree	2.01-3.00	Somewhat	Usually 50% of the time
2	Moderately Disagree	1.01-2.00	Very Little	Usually 10% of the time
1	Strongly Disagree	0.01-1.00	Not at All	Never
0	Neither			

(Scale adopted from Cando, Burdeos, Gonzales, Arlan, Permanes, & Garcia, 2022)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The General Responses of the Single Woman Parents (N=60) on Typology of Strain Perspectives

Table 1 shows the general responses of the single woman parents (n=60) on typology of strain perspectives. When taken as an entire group, the results showed that single woman parents had “Much” extent of motherhood and work ideologies in terms (a) Reinvented motherhood, (b) work–family symbiosis, (c) work–family conflicted motherhood, and (d) work-centered motherhood (M=3.94, SD=.59; M=3.91, SD=.57; M=3.80, SD=.66; M=3.77, SD=.76, respectively). This implies that the respondents usually manifest these four motherhood-workplace negotiation perspectives 90% of the time.

This supports the idea of Thielemans and Mortelmans (2019) on parenthood ideologies in relation to single parenthood that single mothers have to cope with the strain on their motherhood role and take on the role of breadwinner, being the sole earner in the family. Single mothers must face the practical problem of finding a new balance between their roles as employee and parent. Of the 60 items in the questionnaire, the item with the highest mean is “My priority as a mother is to give my child or children a good, consistent upbringing that leads them to become a good human being (M=4.63, SD=.76) and the item with the lowest mean is “I prioritize my work over my child or children (M=2.73, SD=1.48). This implies that single mothers despite parents’ separation or divorce, they hope that their children will consistently have better physical, emotional, and academic well-being. Also, this circumstance is not used by single mothers as the ultimate form of self-development in life after separation although there are some descriptions that work is a means of single mothers to escape after separation like the one stressed out by Gasse & Mortelmans (2020) in their study on single mothers’ perspectives on the combination of motherhood and work. Moreover, the standard deviations for the typology of strain perspectives and the aggregate standard deviation were all less than 3.00. It indicates that there was a close clustering of the responses around the mean (Refugio, Galleto, Noblefranca, Inoferio, Macias, Colina & Dimalig, 2020). It means that there was a greater homogeneity of the single woman mothers’ content extent of motherhood and work ideologies in terms (a) Reinvented motherhood which is a little more dominant than (b) work–family symbiosis, (c) work-centered motherhood, and (d) work–family conflicted motherhood.

Table 1: The General Responses of Single Woman Parents (n=60) on Typology of Strain Perspectives

Typology of Strain Perspectives	M	SD	Verbal Description
A. Re-Invented Single Motherhood			
1. I was struggling with my thoughts when I became a single parent.	4.3833	1.20861	To the Great Extent
2. I am a good mother even when I became a single parent.	4.5000	.67648	To the Great Extent
3. I am a good employee or worker when I became a single parent.	4.4000	.84773	To the Great Extent

4. I was an unachiever in all areas of my life when I became a single parent.	3.1167	1.65797	Much
5. I felt like I am an achiever when I realized that I have been the mother that I wanted to be for my children.	4.5333	.76947	To the Great Extent
6. I did not have the career I dreamt of when I became a single parent.	3.4500	1.26792	Much
7. I was doing my job in my own way when I became a single parent.	4.1667	1.12245	To the Great Extent
8. I changed my motherhood ideologies after divorce or separation.	3.4833	1.28210	Much
9. I have a slim motherhood belief that could be interpreted in a flexible way.	3.1167	1.18023	Much
10. I have a thin motherhood ideologies that could stop me from pursuing unattainable goals in my work and family life.	3.1667	1.29099	Much
11. I exhibit flexibility in my workplace behavior.	4.1500	1.19071	To the Great Extent
12. I look for a job with a more flexible organization of labor.	4.1667	1.26446	To the Great Extent
13. I have a fast-changing work attitude.	4.0500	1.24090	To the Great Extent
14. I have a flexible and family-friendly workplace that ensures I do not experience insurmountable difficulties after divorce or separation.	4.1667	1.02786	To the Great Extent
15. I look for new work where I can adjust the work environment to my changing needs.	4.2833	1.12131	To the Great Extent
\bar{X}	3.94	.59	Much
B. Work–Family Symbiosis			
1. I believe that mothering is about looking for balance.	4.4833	.92958	To the Great Extent
2. My priority as a mother is to give my child or children a good, consistent upbringing that leads them to become a good human being.	4.6333	.75838	To the Great Extent
3. I prioritize my work over my child or children.	2.7333	1.48286	Somewhat
4. I have a good boss who understands my priorities.	3.7333	1.43641	Much
5. I look for jobs that offer a flexibility that enables me to give up few of my motherhood aspirations.	3.8000	1.47062	Much
6. If I look for a new job, I could not negotiate the working hours, or the possibility of working from home, even if the job was as interesting as it could be.	3.6833	.89237	Much
7. I would not take any job that would negotiate the working hours even if the job was as interesting as it could be.	3.5500	1.17061	Much
8. I would risk changing jobs after divorce or separation.	3.6167	1.37892	Much
9. My job is family-friendly in its organization.	4.0333	1.17843	Much
10. I have a strict motherhood belief.	4.0500	.96419	To the Great Extent
11. I have a flexible workplace behavior.	4.1167	1.00998	To the Great Extent
12. I have a combination of strict motherhood beliefs and flexible workplace behavior.	4.1333	.91070	To the Great Extent
13. I have a family-centered lifestyle in which everything is a function of parenting.	4.3167	.87317	To the Great Extent

14. I look for ways to bend my workplace behavior around my firm motherhood ideology, which I remain committed to after divorce or separation.	3.9167	1.12433	Much
15. Having a career is no longer something to which I could aspire.	3.8667	1.32085	Much
\bar{X}	3.91	.57	Much
C. Work-Centered Motherhood			
1. I am a work-centered principled person.	3.8667	1.26848	Much
2. I can still meet the rigid demands of my workplace, while looking for childcare solutions outside my primary family system.	4.1667	.88618	To the Great Extent
3. Being a single parent led me to comfort in my other life project—my job or career.	4.1333	.87269	To the Great Extent
4. When I became a single parent, I locked myself up somewhat at work.	3.5333	1.43168	Much
5. I work hard and I feel so good when my work is appreciated.	4.0167	1.08130	To the Great Extent
6. I let my parents or relatives take care of my children.	4.0500	1.09583	To the Great Extent
7. Sometimes I feel bad when I do not report on duty because I feel I really need to work to provide food on the table for my child or children.	3.8833	1.42724	Much
8. I prefer a full-time job.	3.8333	1.23737	Much
9. I would stay longer and take no breaks in my workplace because I needed the money.	3.6833	1.22808	Much
10. I do not want to do a boring part-time job.	3.5833	1.29263	Much
11. I used work or my job as the ultimate form of self-development in life after divorce or separation.	3.7667	1.28045	Much
12. I am trapped in a rigid work system just to divert my attention after divorce or separation.	3.6333	1.50667	Much
13. I adjust my motherhood ideology towards a slimmer motherhood perspective to deal with the high demands of the workplace.	3.5667	1.53343	Much
14. When I got divorced or separated, I locked myself up somewhat at work.	3.5167	1.62075	Much
15. When I got divorced or separated, I gained less time for my children.	3.3667	1.59413	Much
\bar{X}	3.77	.76	Much
D. Work–Family Conflicted Motherhood			
1. I retain a strict motherhood belief while still meeting the demands of my job.	3.6500	1.40006	Much
2. I always run out of energy when I am home after my work.	3.1833	1.54582	Much
3. I cannot be a good mother anymore because I am always busy.	3.6167	1.62701	Much
4. As a single parent, I have to work hard to keep my current job to support my child or children.	3.8167	1.06551	Much
5. As a single parent, I cannot do the things I want to do to be the mother I want to be.	3.5833	1.29263	Much
6. I am a family-centered mother who is simply not able to adjust my work environment in accordance with my strict motherhood ideology	3.8167	1.26881	Much

7. I do not compromise my motherhood ideology for my work.	4.0000	.99149	Much
8. I have a fear of change in the work environment.	3.8833	1.07501	Much
9. I have a fear of the consequences of adjusting my motherhood ideology.	3.8167	1.11221	Much
10. Because of my fear of change in the work environment, I choose the security of a job I know, although this is incompatible with my new family life situation.	3.9833	.94764	Much
11. I have a lot of insecurities about my job and family as a single parent.	3.4000	1.48666	Much
12. My motherhood ideologies and work are in conflict.	3.6500	1.47090	Much
13. As a single parent, I have a lot of aspirations for my child/children	4.3167	.87317	To the Great Extent
14. I can still cope with the demands of a job despite being a single parent.	4.3000	.74333	To the Great Extent
15. I always encounter a problematic situation because my motherhood ideologies and work are in conflict.	3.9667	1.02456	Much
\bar{X}	3.80	.66	Much

The Typology of Strain Perspectives of Single Woman Parents (N=60) when Grouped as to Age, Education, and Number of Children

The results further showed that the respondents whose age belonged to 20-40 years old category had “Much” extent of motherhood and work ideologies in terms (a) Reinvented motherhood and (b) work–family symbiosis (M=3.80, SD=.59; M=3.80, SD=.44, respectively). However, work–family conflicted motherhood is little more dominant than (d) work-centered motherhood (M=3.73, SD=.36 and M=3.55, SD=.69, respectively).

On the other hand, single woman parents who are 40 years old and above had also “Much” extent of motherhood and work ideologies in terms (a) Reinvented motherhood which is little more dominant than (b) work–family symbiosis. In addition, work-centered motherhood is a little more dominant than (d) work–family conflicted motherhood (M=3.98 SD=.60 and M=3.94, SD=.61; M=3.55, SD=.69; M=3.73, SD=.36, respectively).

This result is congruent with the study of Kim and Kim (2020) which states that the ages of the single mothers has relation with the amount of struggles they face. Teenage single mothers are said to have a harder time earning money for their household compared to single mothers who are between ages of 30 to 50.

When grouped as to education, the results showed that the respondents with college degree had “To the Great Extent” of motherhood and work ideologies in terms (a) Reinvented motherhood (M=4.09, SD=.33) and “Much” extent typology of strain perspectives on (b) work–family symbiosis, (c) work-centered motherhood, and (d) work–family conflicted motherhood (M=3.97, SD=.46; M=3.65, SD=.73 and M=3.80, SD=.36, respectively). On the other hand, single woman parents without college degree had “Much” extent of motherhood and work ideologies in terms (a) Reinvented motherhood which is a little more dominant than (b) work–family symbiosis, (c) work-centered motherhood, and (d) work–family conflicted motherhood (M=3.90, SD=.64; M=3.90, SD=.60; M=3.81, SD=.77; M=3.80, SD=.72, respectively). This implies that the

single woman mothers with college degree manifest the lean motherhood ideology and flexible workplace behavior most of the time. Additionally, work–family symbiosis, work-centered motherhood, and work–family conflicted motherhood are apparent 90% of the time.

When grouped as to number of children, the results showed that the respondents with only one child had “To the Great Extent” of motherhood and work ideologies in terms (a) work–family symbiosis ($M=4.01$, $SD=.46$) and “Much” extent typology of strain perspectives on (b) Reinvented motherhood, (c) work-centered motherhood, and (d) work–family conflicted motherhood ($M=3.94$, $SD=.57$; $M=3.71$, $SD=.80$ and $M=3.76$, $SD=.67$, respectively). On the other hand, single woman parents with 2 more children had “Much” extent of motherhood and work ideologies in terms (a) Reinvented motherhood which is a little more dominant than (b) work–family symbiosis, (c) work-centered motherhood, and (d) work–family conflicted motherhood ($M=3.95$, $SD=.63$; $M=3.79$, $SD=.68$; $M=3.85$, $SD=.71$; $M=3.85$, $SD=.65$, respectively). This implies that the single woman mothers with only one child manifest a perspective that is characterized by a family-centered work ethic most of the time. Additionally, work–family symbiosis, work-centered motherhood, and work–family conflicted motherhood are apparent 90% of the time.

Differences in the Typology of Strain Perspectives of Single Woman Parents (N=60) when Grouped as to Age, Education, and Number of Children

A Mann-Whitney U test was performed to evaluate whether there was a significant difference in the typology of strain perspective of single woman parents in terms of (a) Reinvented motherhood (b) work–family symbiosis, (c) work-centered motherhood, and (d) work–family conflicted motherhood when grouped according to age, education, and number of children.

The results indicated that there was no significant difference in the typology of strain perspective of single woman parents in terms of (a) Reinvented motherhood, (b) work–family symbiosis, (c) work-centered motherhood, and (d) work–family conflicted motherhood when grouped according to age $U = [251.50; 252.00; 255.00; 266.00]$, $p = [.331; .336; .364; \text{and } .478]$; education $U = [258.00; 286.50; 278.00; 299.00]$, $p = [.393; .733; .621; \text{and } .907]$, and number of children $U = [428.50; 361.00; 418.50; 379.50]$, $p = [.800; .208; .688; \text{and } .326]$.

This supports the hypothesis stating that there are no statistically significant variations that exist in the motherhood–workplace negotiation perspectives of solo parents in terms of (a) Reinvented motherhood, (b) work–family symbiosis, (c) work-centered motherhood, and (d) work–family conflicted motherhood when categorized as to socio-economic elements such as age, education, employment, and number of children.

However, this finding does not find support from the survey of The Ministry of Gender Equality and Family as cited by Kim & Kim (202) which reported that vulnerable single parents with low education were more likely to experience depressive symptoms and report worse subjective health conditions. Also, in the study of Van de Velde, Bambra,

Vander Bracht, Eikemo, & Bracke as cited by Kim & Kim 9202) which found that lower education were associated with poor health in single mothers.

Results of the Qualitative Study

Research Objectives	Themes
RO3: Determine the challenges do single woman parents face as they do their job	Challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emotionally challenged: Unable to manage their emotions sufficiently Financially Challenged: Lack of financial means to meet their obligations as single mothers Financial Management: Unable to manage their small income for their daily needs Time management – Unable to manage their time for work, time to perform obligations, and time for bonding with children “<i>Marites</i>”: Their private lives are being talked about by other people Flexibility: Unable to focus on work and family. They lack efficiency
RO4: Determine the internal and external drivers of women solo parents that allow them to face the challenges of balancing work and family	Internal and External Drivers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physical attachment with their children Emotional attachment with their children (feeling of empathy) Self-motivation Family support Friends Faith and Devotion Occupation (Work or Job) Financial Deficiency to support their children Future of their children Personal ideology
RO5: Determine the support systems do women solo parents utilize to achieve work-life balance	Support Systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dream job or career Relationship with their siblings, children and friends
RO6: Determine the management strategies (other life domains) do women solo parents utilize to achieve work-life balance	Management Strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manage your time Balance time and work Ask assistance or help from someone Refit daily wages or budget regular income Seek parental support Have an extra job Be not picky about work Raise independent kids

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. When taken as an entire group, single mothers manifest the four motherhood-workplace negotiation perspectives: (a) Reinvented motherhood, (b) work–family

symbiosis, (c) work–family conflicted motherhood, and (d) work-centered motherhood 90% of the time.

2. Despite parents' separation or divorce, single mothers hope that their children will consistently have better physical, emotional, and academic well-being. Also, this circumstance is not used by single mothers as the ultimate form of self-development in life after separation although there are some descriptions that work is a means of single mothers to escape after separation.
3. The four motherhood and work ideologies are dominant among single mothers whose age belonged to 20-40 years old 90% of the time. However, they are more likely to retain a strict motherhood ideology while still meeting the demands of a rigid workplace than those who are 40 years old and above, who are work-centered ethic than the former. This means that single mothers who are 40 years old and above rigorously meet the rigid demands of their workplace, while looking for childcare solutions outside their primary family system. This further explains that, the older single mothers become, the more they find solace or relief in their job or career.
4. Single mother with college degree have a lean motherhood ideology and flexible workplace behavior every time and 90% dominant with other typology of strain perspectives. On the other hand, single woman parents without college degree manifest the four motherhood and work ideologies 90% of the time. This mean that education brands single mothers as individuals with lean motherhood ideology and flexible workplace behavior. In other words, the more educated single mother are, the more they achieve work–life balance through a flexible work environment.
5. Single mother with only one child have a lean motherhood ideology and flexible workplace behavior every time and 90% dominant with other typology of strain perspectives. On the other hand, single woman parents with 2 or more children manifest the four motherhood and work ideologies 90% of the time. This mean that having one child in the family brands single mothers as individuals with lean motherhood ideology and flexible workplace behavior. In other words, the more children single mother have, the more likely they cannot achieve work–life balance through a flexible work environment.
6. Regardless of age, education, and number of children, there is no statistically significant difference on the prevailing typology of strain perspectives of single woman parents. Their mean scores have a little difference but the interpretation of the level of their motherhood and work ideologies are just the same.
7. Single mothers are unable to manage their emotions sufficiently. They lack of financial means to meet their obligations and unable to manage their small income for their daily needs. In addition, single mothers are unable to manage their time for work, time to perform obligations, and time for bonding with children. They are also unable to focus on work and family that results to lack of efficiency. The most repulsive is, their private lives are being talked about by other people.

8. The Key drivers of effective single woman parents that allow them to face the challenges of balancing work and family were physical and emotional attachment, self-motivation, family support, friends, devotion, work, and personal ideology.
9. To achieve balance in work and family, single woman parents manage their time, ask assistance or help from someone, refit daily wages or budget regular income, seek parental support, do extra job, are not selective about work, and raise independent kids.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are recommendations based on the foregoing conclusions:

1. All single mothers may find support systems to help manage their daily challenges. These support systems can be family and friends who are willing to help out, work environment, devotion and personal ideology. It would also be beneficial for the local government to have programs in improving the work-life balance of single woman parents and create more support systems through networking opportunities, social support groups, counseling services, offering emotional and practical assistance.
2. Single-mother are vulnerable to hardships in finding the time, money, and other resources needed to provide for their families. Therefore, the government may provide a start-up capital for the livelihood of single mothers such as furniture making, gardening, massage therapy, food production and processing, salon and spa, and poultry production.
3. The researcher recommends that a successful employment program dedicated to providing single mothers with skills and knowledge maybe made, helping single mothers find long-term, stable employment. This program may provide weekend training workshops and coaching sessions wherein single mothers learn about topics such as financial assessment, résumé preparation, and job interviewing.
4. A research on the implementation of Republic Act No. 8972, an act providing for the benefits and privileges to solo parents and their children may be conducted (Statement of a single mother during the interview: *“Hard to find job due to status because most of the companies looked for those who can extend time for work which the solo parent cannot. Because for us we consider our time to our children.”*)
5. An impact study on Solo Parent Cash Aid, a government’s financial assistance program parallel to Republic Act No. 8972 which is dedicated to offering support to solo parents, maybe an interest for future researchers to identify its implementation, benefits and other key components tailored to the needs of the beneficiaries (Statement of a single mother during the interview: *“kabudlay mangita ka kwarta, ginauna ang pagkaon kag pag eswela kag naga asa guid sa ayoda ka gobyerno kag tani matalupangdan man.”---it is very hard to earn an income, I prioritize food and schooling, and I am dependent on the subsidy of the government and we may receive immediate attention*)

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